

CNT-EFFECTED GLASS FIBRE SIZINGS FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY

For the development of glass fibre sizing systems bearing the potential to form electrically conductive interphases in fibre reinforced composites, model systems, based on carbon nanotubes in polymeric film formers were investigated with regard to their electrical resistivity. Although the systems showed low resistivities, the results could not be transferred directly to the spinning of glass fibres, due to the issue of inhomogeneous fibre coating and the comparably low absolute amount of polymeric film former on the fibre.

Keywords: glass fibre, sizing, CNT, dispersion, nanocomposite

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNT) have caused a great deal of interest as fillers for polymeric materials. This is mainly based on their set of exceptional properties [1-3], making them highly versatile for modifying and tailoring material properties. As a consequence, research activities have been started covering a wide range of topics, e.g. synthesis and functionalisation of CNT, modelling and experimental determination of their properties, dispersion in thermoplastics and thermosets, and the preparation and characterisation of CNT-based nanocomposites.

It is well known that reinforcing polymers by dispersed CNT has a beneficial effect on the mechanical properties of nanocomposites and numerous publications are available on the incorporation of CNT into different matrices [4-6]. However, besides the excellent stiffness and strength of CNT making them valuable as mechanical reinforcement, other properties, like their electrical conductivity, make them attractive for achieving functional properties in polymers. In the field of thermoplastics, issues of processing and characterisation of electrically conductive CNT-based nanocomposites have been addressed [4,7,8] similarly as for thermosets, where networks of percolated CNT within the matrix have been used for strain-sensing and health monitoring of fibre reinforced composites [9,10-12].

Besides the use of CNT in the bulk matrix of fibre reinforced composites, their application in the fibre-matrix interphase has been proved to result in beneficial mechanical properties [13,14]. For manufacturing composites with CNT present solely in the interphase, rather than being distributed in the bulk, CNT are applied during glass fibre (GF) spinning within aqueous sizings onto the surface of the GF. Consequently, upon consolidation of the composites in a second step, the wetting of the fibres by the

matrix results in fibre reinforced composites where the CNT are located in their interphase. The presence of CNT affects the load transfer from the matrix into the fibre and involves additional failure mechanisms inherent to CNT in the interphase. Moreover, for semi-crystalline thermoplastics as isotactic polypropylene (PP), the nucleating ability of CNT results in transcrystalline interphases in the composites [13,15].

However, apart from beneficial effects of CNT on the mechanical properties of composites, it is desirable to further explore the potential of CNT for realising multifunctional properties in the composites. Therefore, this work focuses on the development of GF-sizings intended to create electrically conductive interphases in composites for interphasial strain-sensing and health monitoring.

At this stage, this comprises the investigation of compression moulded films made of polymeric film former containing CNT with regard to their electrical resistivity for identifying the electrical percolation threshold of CNT in the corresponding systems. As the CNT are applied onto the GF surface within aqueous sizings, effective dispersion in aqueous media is a necessary prerequisite for achieving both, increased mechanical performance and a certain electrical conductivity in the sizing layer. Therefore, this study describes the manufacturing of the CNT-filled films starting off with dispersing CNT in aqueous media using surfactants, mixing the pre-dispersed CNT with the polymeric film former following a latex-approach, and ending up with compression moulding the obtained powder into thin films, which are characterised with regard to their electrical resistivity.

EXPERIMENTAL

Different grades of multi-walled CNT, namely NC3150, NC3151, and NC3101 (Nanocyl S.A., Belgium) were added to surfactant solution and treated with a horn sonicator for 120 min at constant output power of 40 W. NC3150 denotes non-functionalised CNT with an average length below 1 μm , whereas the NC3151 and NC3101 represent carboxy-functionalised CNT having average lengths below 1 μm and around 1.5 μm , respectively. The aqueous surfactant solution was prepared dissolving sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS; Sigma Aldrich) or Brij76 (Sigma Aldrich) in deionised water. In both cases the surfactant to CNT ratio was adjusted to 1.5/1, using 0.3 wt% CNT in 100 ml deionised water.

Throughout sonication the beaker with the CNT was cooled in a water bath. Samples of the dispersion were taken in regular time intervals and diluted with deionised water (1:50) before recording UV-vis spectra (Perkin Elmer Lambda 800). The spectra were captured using a blank filled with deionised water. None of the surfactants used contributes to the determined maximum absorbance values of the CNT at about 259 nm.

In the next step, different quantities of pre-dispersed CNT were added to a PP-film former (Permanol 602, Clariant) and a polyurethane (PU)-based film former (Neoxil 9851, DSM composite resins AG, Switzerland). In order to homogenise the system, the pre-dispersed CNT and the film former were magnetically stirred for several minutes. Afterwards, the system was freeze dried (Alpha 1-2 LD plus, Christ GmbH, Germany) and the obtained powder was used for compression moulding of the films (K207, Rucks GmbH, Germany). In detail, the powder was heated from ambient temperature to

200 °C with 15 K/min including a degassing step at 180 °C. After having reached 200 °C, the films were compression moulded at 30 bar for 2 min, before cooling down to room temperature.

E-glass fibres having an average diameter of 15 µm were continuously spun at the Leibniz-Institute of Polymer Research Dresden. An aqueous sizing consisting of PP-film former and pre-dispersed NC3101 was applied onto the GF during the spinning.

Volume resistivity measurements of the 80 µm thick films were conducted using a 4-point test fixture in combination with the electrometers 6517a and DMM2000 (Keithley Instruments Inc.), respectively, allowing to measure resistivities of up to 10^{12} Ωcm. The films were cut into pieces of about 30 x 25 mm² and measured separately. The presented values are mean values of at least 4 measurements. The electrical resistivity of the GF was measured using a 8002a high resistivity test fixture in combination with the electrometer 6517a (both by Keithley Instruments Inc.).

The SEM images were obtained using an Ultra 55 (Carl Zeiss SMT AG, Germany), after sputtering a 5 nm thick platinum layer onto the as-spun GF.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dispersing CNT in aqueous media

As the performance of any nanocomposite is strongly related to the distribution and dispersion of its nanoparticles, it is of importance to assure a good state of dispersion of the CNT. Therefore, for the application of CNT in GF-sizings efficient pre-dispersion of the CNT in aqueous media is desirable before mixing the CNT with the polymeric film former in a subsequent step.

The evaluation of the degree of dispersion of CNT in aqueous media can be achieved by recording UV-vis spectra of the dispersions. Since individualised CNT show characteristic bands in the UV region [16,17], the measured absorbance at a specific wavelength can be related to their degree of exfoliation [18-20]. Figure 1 shows the dependence of maximum UV-vis absorbance on sonication time. The inset of Figure 1 depicts the evolution of the UV-vis spectra with increasing sonication times, showing clearly the maximum of absorbance at a wavelength of ~259 nm due to the presence of individualised CNT.

With increasing sonication time the absorbance in the characteristic wavelength region changes to higher values. Plotting the maximum absorbance at a specific wavelength versus sonication time, the dispersion process of the CNT can be monitored, showing a characteristic pattern with rapidly increasing absorbance values for short sonication times before a plateau-like behaviour is observed and ongoing sonication does not result in a further increase of absorbance.

Influence of CNT-dispersion in aqueous media on the resistivity

If the resistivity of CNT-nanocomposites is regarded, it is not surprising to find a correlation of the state of dispersion with the measured resistivity values of the compression moulded films. It can be assumed that for ideally dispersed CNT and weight fractions above the percolation threshold the values of the resistivity are

Fig. 1: Dependence of maximum UV-vis absorbance at a wavelength of 259 nm on sonication time for NC3101 suspended in SDS. Inset: UV-vis spectra of NC3101 suspended in SDS for different sonication times

minimised. For poorer dispersion qualities, the fraction of effectively dispersed and distributed CNT becomes smaller and an increasing amount of CNT is present in form of primary agglomerates not contributing to the conductive network formed by the CNT. At a certain point, the effective amount of CNT for forming conductive paths in the matrix falls below the percolation threshold of the system and the resistivity increases sharply. Figure 2 shows dependence of maximum UV-absorbance and resistivity of the compression moulded films on the sonication time of CNT dispersed in aqueous media for a constant CNT weight fraction. For the given constant weight fraction of 1% NC3101 the achieved state of dispersion for different sonication times is reflected in the obtained resistivity values of the corresponding compression moulded films. This indicates that by mixing the pre-dispersed CNT with the polymeric film former the state of dispersion of the CNT is maintained and defines the range of the resistivity values observed. Especially between 5 and 20 min a pronounced drop in the resistivity is observed which coincides with the rapid increase in absorbance for those sonication times. After the resistivity value has dropped almost 4 orders of magnitude between 5 and 20 min, longer sonication times result only in a modest further decrease down to $\sim 10^5 \Omega\text{cm}$. For the given CNT weight fraction additional sonication does not change this value substantially. At first glance, it might be surprising that resistivity has reached its minimum already after about 40 min, but as the concentration of 1 wt% NC3101 is above the electrical percolation threshold of this system (cf. fig. 3), it is sufficient that only a certain part of the CNT is efficiently dispersed for reaching the lowest resistivities, whereas the quantification of the state of dispersion by means of

UV-vis spectroscopy indicates, that after 60-80 min sonication dispersion quality has reached its maximum (cf. fig. 1). For lower constant weight fractions this should be different as a higher amount of all CNT has to be dispersed efficiently in order to result in lowest resistivity values. Consequently, the sonication time for the lowest resistivity values should be closer to the sonication times resulting in constant UV-vis absorbance.

Fig. 2: UV-vis absorbance at a wavelength of 259 nm for differently pre-dispersed NC3101 in aqueous solution of SDS and obtained resistivity values for the corresponding compression moulded films made by mixing pre-dispersed CNT with PP-film former. CNT weight fraction is 1 wt% for all films

Influence of different CNT-grades on resistivity

As CNT have the potential to result in tailored electrical properties, the effect of different CNT grades on the electrical resistivity is investigated. Literature reports that by means of functionalisation the dispersibility of CNT is increased as well as an increase in mechanical properties can be observed, as this allows for a covalent bonding between the CNT and the matrix [6,21]. However, this can damage the structure of CNT and dispersibility increases at the expense of mechanical and electrical properties of CNT. Irrespective of whether the electrical percolation threshold or the effect on mechanical properties is regarded, besides the functionalisation of CNT the aspect ratio plays an important role. Assuming a statistical distribution of particles in an excluded volume concept, the percolation threshold is inversely proportional to the aspect ratio of the particles [22]. Thus, a higher aspect ratio is supposed to result in a lower percolation threshold. Ignoring any particle movement upon consolidation, the statistical percolation threshold of CNT with an aspect ratio of 1000 is about 0.1 wt%, assuming

Fig. 3: Dependency of resistivity on CNT weight fraction for different CNT grades in films made by mixing pre-dispersed CNT with PP-film former

fully individualized and statistically distributed particles. Figure 3 shows for different CNT-grades the influence of different aspect ratios as well as the effect of functionalisation on the electrical resistivity. NC3151 and NC3101 denote COOH-functionalised CNT. According to the data sheet, the former one has an average length below 1 μm and the latter one of 1.5 μm . NC3150 is similar to the NC3151 in terms of dimensions, but is non-functionalised. Comparing the two COOH-functionalised CNT with regard to the achieved resistivities, no major difference can be observed, however, films based on NC3151 show even slightly lower resistivities. This is somewhat unexpected, as NC3151 have a lower aspect ratio compared to NC3101. Most likely, the difference is due to experimental reasons upon dispersing the CNT as the macroscopic grain size of the two grades is very different, being much coarser for the NC3101. The absence of a clear trend towards lower resistivities for higher aspect ratios can be related to the damage and shortening of the CNT upon sonication [23-25]. In a recent work, CNT with strongly differing dimensions have been investigated in polystyrene films, produced following a latex approach [26]. Although the initial difference in length was up to a factor of 10, after sonication both CNT grades showed average lengths in the same range. This was explained by the higher forces acting on longer CNT during sonication, making them prone to cavitation-induced scission, while shorter CNT are less affected by this phenomenon [27].

The non-functionalised NC3150 show a rather different behaviour compared to the functionalised CNT-grades. Although they have been dispersed in aqueous solution of Brij76, whereas the COOH-functionalised grades were dispersed in aqueous solution of SDS, this is not supposed to have a major influence on the results. UV-vis spectroscopy indicates a similar state of dispersion of the CNT for identical sonication parameters,

independent of whether using NC3150/Brij76, NC3151/SDS or NC3101/SDS [28]. Moreover, resistivity measurements on the PP-films without CNT but with the surfactants show that at concentrations as they were used for the films containing CNT, both surfactants do not have considerable effects on the resistivity. Slightly lower values for the SDS-filled system compared to the unfilled PP-film are possibly due to the anionic character of SDS. However, already at a concentration of 0.2 wt% NC3150 the resistivity of the system is more than one order of magnitude lower than the one containing 0.5 wt% NC3101. For comparable weight fractions of CNT the difference in resistivity between films based on the non-functionalised NC3150 and the COOH-functionalised grades is about 3 orders of magnitude, resulting in values of $\sim 5 \Omega\text{cm}$ for 3 wt% NC3150.

Challenges in application of conductive sizings onto GF

When using the systems as sizings for GF with the intention to form electrically conductive interphases, low resistivity values are generally desirable for keeping the electrical resistance in a reasonable measurement range. The resistivity measurements on the films can be regarded as model systems allowing to identify suitable sizing systems for further application onto the GF. Although the obtained resistivity values of the films show a distinct decrease in resistivity with higher CNT content, the transfer to the GF-spinning poses multiple challenges. Figure 4a shows a schematic view of an ideally and inhomogeneously sized GF. In the upper part of figure 4a the GF is homogeneously covered by the sizing, resulting in a thin, but continuous layer of conductive sizing on the surface of the GF. Contrary to that, inhomogeneous coating of the GF leading to a discontinuous sizing layer is shown in the lower part of figure 4a. This indicates that a simple lowering of the resistivity by addition of CNT to GF-sizings is not sufficient for achieving electrical conductivity in the interphase of GF reinforced composites and can rather be regarded as a necessary prerequisite. Only in combination with a good film formation as well as a sufficiently high amount of film former on the GF it will be possible to realise electrically conductive interphases. The organic content of the sized GF, representing the electrically conductive nanocomposite, can be varied in a certain range. Figure 4b shows the variation of the organic content of the sized GF as a function of film former content within the dispersion for a PP- and PU-film former. For both systems an increase of organic content on the GF with increasing amount of film former in the dispersion is observed. Besides the mere change of the sizing formulation, a variation of GF-spinning parameters, e.g. the haul-off velocity, could affect the results as well, but is beyond the scope of this study. From figure 4b it becomes obvious that the PP-film former results in a lower organic content on the fibres than the PU-film former, although for both the determined content of solid particles is about 35 wt%. This is related to the superior film formation of the PU-film former, resulting in a more complete coverage of the GF, whereas the PP-film former is comparably brittle and tends to peel off. Figures 4c and 4d show SEM images of as spun GF sized with PP- and PU-film former, respectively. In figure 4c the peel off marks can clearly be seen on the surface of the sized GF for the more brittle PP-film former, whereas similar observations can not be made for the PU-film former, which is soft and flexible at room temperature due to its low glass transition temperature. However, although the coverage of the GF with the PU-film former is comparably good, irregularly shaped accumulations of film former can be observed on the GF. The

Fig. 4: a) Schematic view of an ideally and inhomogeneously sized glass fibre (axial and longitudinal cross section); b) organic content on as spun GF for different film formers and film former contents in the dispersion; c) SEM image of as spun GF with 10.5 wt% PP-film former in the dispersion; d) SEM image of as spun GF with 17.5 wt% PU-film former in the dispersion

determination of the resistivity of as spun GF, sized with the PP-film former and having an organic content of approximately 2 wt%, out of which 2 wt% are NC3101, results in values of approximately $8.88 \cdot 10^8 \Omega\text{cm}$, which is considerably higher than the values determined for the film, being in the range of 10^4 - $10^5 \Omega\text{cm}$ (cf. Fig.3). Firstly, this is likely to be related to the issue of proper contacting all GF within the yarn. Secondly, the resistance is determined on a measurement length of 60 mm and converted into resistivity by $\rho = R \cdot A / l$, with ρ being the resistivity, R the measured resistance, A the effective cross section of the conductive sizing within the yarn, and l the measurement length. The calculation of A , assuming a homogeneous coverage of the GF on the whole measurement length, is based on the determined organic content of the yarn. However, taking into account the measurement length of 60 mm of the test fixture used, inhomogeneities are likely to be present on that distance. The observed peel off of the film former (cf. Fig 4c) and therefore absence of conductive paths in some regions of the GF-yarn results in an effective cross sectional area which is supposed to be considerably smaller than the one calculated from the amount of film former on the GF-yarn assuming homogeneous coverage.

The aim of the future work is the spinning of sized GF with lower electrical resistivities. Therefore, the use of different film former systems containing non-functionalised CNT

should result in both, lower resistivity of the sizing itself as well as an increased organic content on the fibres.

CONCLUSIONS

Dispersing CNT in aqueous media using surfactants allows to incorporate pre-dispersed CNT into polymeric film former systems and to apply them during the GF-spinning within an aqueous sizing onto the surface of GF. In order to develop sizing systems with the potential to form electrically conductive interphases in fibre reinforced composites, model systems, based on compression moulded films made of polymeric film former containing CNT, were prepared following a latex-approach and investigated with regard to their electrical properties.

For a constant weight fraction of CNT a correlation between the state of dispersion of the CNT in aqueous media, achieved by different sonication times, and the resistivity of the films was observed. Investigating the effect of different CNT-grades on the resistivity of PP-films, a higher aspect ratio of the CNT was not found to lower the resistivity. Rather the use of non-functionalised CNT bears the potential to substantially lower the resistivity values of the films, compared with the COOH-functionalised CNT. Although the obtained resistivities of the films with the non-functionalised CNT range in the order of 10^1 - 10^2 Ω cm and show an electrical percolation threshold well below 0.5 wt%, these results can not be transferred directly to spun GF, sized with a PP-film former system containing CNT. When it comes to the application of the electrically conductive sizing onto the GF during spinning, the measured resistivity of the GF-yarn is not only determined by the intrinsic resistivity of the CNT-sizing system, but mainly influenced by the absolute amount of organic content on the GF, forming conductive paths on the surface of the GF, and being dependent on the wetting ability of the sizing. Thus, the determined resistivity of an as spun GF-yarn sized with pre-dispersed CNT and PP-film former is considerably higher than the resistivity of a comparable compression moulded film.

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References

1. Coleman JN, Khan U, Blau WJ, Gun'ko YK. Carbon 2006;44(9):1624-1652
2. Du JH, Bai J, Cheng HM. eXPRESS Polym Lett 2007;1(5):253-273
3. Bauhofer W, Kovacs J. Comp Sci Techn 2008; Article in press: doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.06.018
4. Pegel S, Pötschke P, Petzold G, Alig I, Dudkin S, Lellinger D. Polymer 2008; 49 (4): 974-984

5. Gojny F, Wichmann M, Fiedler B, Schulte K. *Comp Sci Techn* 2005; 65 (15-16): 2300-2313
6. Moniruzzaman M, Winey K. *Polymer Nanocomposites containing carbon nanotubes*. *Macromolecules* 2006; 39 (16): 5194-5205
7. Krause B, Petzold G, Pegel S, Pötschke P. *Correlation of carbon nanotube dispersability in aqueous surfactant solutions and polymers*. *Carbon* 2009; 47 (3): 602-612
8. Grossiord N, Kivitt P, Loos P, Meuldijk J, Kyrlyuk A, van der Schoot P, Koning C. *Polymer* 2008; 49 (12): 2866-2872
9. Böger L, Wichmann M, Meyer L, Schulte K. *Comp Sci Techn* 68 2008; 68 (7-8): 1886–1894.
10. Wichmann M, Buschhorn S, Böger L, Adlung R, Schulte K. *Nanotechnology* 2008; 19 (47): 1-5
11. Thostenson E, Chou T. *Advanced Materials* 2006; 18 (21): 2837-2841
12. Thostenson E, Chou T. *Nanotechnology* 2008; 19 (21): 1-6
13. Mäder, E., Rausch, J., and Schmidt, N. 2008. *Composites: Part A* 2008 ; 39 (4): 612-623
14. Rausch, J., Zhuang, R., and Mäder, E. 2009. *Materials Technology* 2009; 1 (24): 29-35
15. Zhang S, Minus M, Zhu L, Wong C, Kumar S. *Polymer* 2008; 49 (5): 1356-1364
16. Saito R, Fujita M, Dresselhaus G, Dresselhaus MS. *Appl Phys Lett* 1992; 60 (18): 2204–6
17. Kataura H, Kumazawa Y, Maniwa Y, Umezue I, Suzuki S, Ohtsuka Y, et al. *Synth Met* 1999; 103: 2555–8
18. Yu J, Grossiord N, Koning CE, Loos J. *Carbon* 2007; 45 (3):618-623
19. Grossiord N, Regev O, Loos J, Meuldijk J, Koning CE. *Anal Chem* 2005; 77 (16): 5135-5139
20. Jiang L, Gao L, Sun J. *J Colloid and Interface Sci* 2003; 260 (1):89-94
21. Banerjee S, Hemraj-Benny T, Wong S. *Advanced Materials* 2005; 17 (1): 17-29
22. Balberg I, Anderson CH, Alexander S, Wagner N. *Phys Rev B* 1984; 30 (7): 3933–43
23. Islam MF, Rojas E, Bergey DM, Johnson AT, Yodh AG. *Nano Letters* 2003; 3 (2): 269-273
24. Huang W, Lin Y, Taylor S, Gaillard J, Rao A, Sun, Y. 2002. *Nano Letters* 2002; 2 (3): 231-234
25. Lu K, Lago R, Chen Y, Green M, Harris P, Tsang S. *Carbon* 1996; 34 (6): 814-816
26. Grossiord N, Loos J, von Laake J, Maugey M, Zakri C, Koning C, Hart J. *Advanced Functional Materials* 2008; 18 (20): 3226–3234

27. Hennrich F, Krupke R, Arnold K, Rojas Stütz JA, Lebedkin S, Koch T, Schimmel T, Kappes MM. *J Phys Chem B* 2007, 111 (8), 1932-37
28. Rausch J, Zhuang RC, Mäder E. *Carbon*; submitted